

Highlights Report

2025

Belgian Biodiversity Platform
For Science, Policy, and Practice

With the support of BELSPO, Belgian Science Policy Office

FOREWORD

As we reflect on 2025, it is clear that this year has been marked by both uncertainty and determination for biodiversity science-policy in Belgium and beyond. The urgency of the biodiversity and climate crises remains ever-present, yet the broader national context has been characterised by ongoing uncertainty. Institutional tensions and extended negotiations have at times complicated efforts to maintain consistent and coordinated policy processes. Despite this, the commitment of the biodiversity community has not wavered. On the contrary, this context has underscored the importance of resilient, well-connected science-policy interfaces capable of sustaining progress even in times of disruption. At the European and global levels, biodiversity action continued to advance. The implementation phase of key international frameworks, including the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, required sustained efforts to translate ambitious targets into concrete actions. Scientific input and coordinated engagement remained essential to ensure that these commitments are grounded in robust evidence and informed by diverse knowledge systems.

In Belgium, the contrasted backdrop of instability made the work of connecting science, policy, and practice all the more critical. Throughout the year, the Platform maintained and strengthened its role as a facilitator and knowledge broker, ensuring continuity in engagement with major global initiatives such as IPBES, IUCN, GBIF, and European-funded projects while also fostering collaboration across sectors and disciplines. By organising key events, supporting international processes, and advancing tools and data infrastructures, the Platform continued to enable informed decision-making and collective action.

We have continued our efforts to improve data and knowledge accessibility, interoperability, and usability which have contributed to a more solid evidence base for biodiversity governance. At the same time, we have been increasing our attention towards bridging gaps: between disciplines, between knowledge systems, and between global processes and national realities.

As we move forward, the lessons of 2025 are clear. Stability cannot be taken for granted, but resilience can be built. In this context, the role of the science-policy interface is more important than ever: to provide continuity, to support informed decisions, and to ensure that biodiversity remains a priority even amidst competing pressures. We remain grateful to our core funding organisation, BELSPO, as well as our host institutions for their continued support and collaboration towards the important work of the Platform.

This 2025 Highlights Report presents a selective overview of key achievements and developments over the past year, illustrating how the Platform has contributed to advancing biodiversity science, policy, and practice. In this edition, we have introduced a new format that emphasises how our work contributes to advancing our mission and strategic objectives, moving beyond a simple account of tasks and events.

We sincerely thank all those who have contributed to these efforts and look forward to continuing this important work together.

Enjoy the read!

Divija Jata
Coordinator

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Our Mission

Decision-making on biodiversity issues is grounded on sound evidence and takes place through collaboration between actors.

INTRODUCTION

The Belgian Biodiversity Platform (BBPf, hereafter “the Platform”) serves as a science-policy interface, funded by the Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO) and supported by a Cooperation Agreement between federal and relevant federated authorities.

Acting at the intersection of science, policy, and practice within the complex field of biodiversity, the Platform addresses challenges through five main topical issues: Ecosystems and Society, Biological Invasions, Biodiversity and Climate Change, One Health, and Biodiversity Conservation.

Our multidisciplinary team is composed of communications officers, science-policy experts, open data officers, and IT experts. The Platform operates across several host institutes at federal and regional levels in Belgium. These strategic placements ensure a strong institutional anchoring and reinforce the Platform’s capacity to fulfil its mandate.

In 2025, the Platform consolidated its position within both the Belgian and global biodiversity landscapes, reaffirming its central role in the biodiversity science-policy interface world.

This was achieved through the co-organisation of events engaging stakeholders across national, European, and international contexts; the development or strengthening of connections with other sectors; Belgian participation and influence in major initiatives such as IUCN, IPBES, Biodiversa+, and GBIF; and the development of tools and knowledge outputs guiding policymakers and practitioners in better decision-making.

This year, we adopted a different approach to reporting on our 2025 activities and achievements, by selecting highlights that are both representative of and relevant to our work and aligned with our core long-term objectives.

Our 4 working areas (*light green circles*)
and our 5 topical issues (*dark green round icons*)

HIGHLIGHTS

ENGAGING THE BIODIVERSITY COMMUNITY

One Health conference

Ecosystems are a fundamental component of the One Health concept, yet their integration into the One Health approach is still largely lacking. Recognising this important gap, the Platform, in close collaboration with Sciensano and FPS Health, organised the **Belgian One Health** (BeOH) event **Ecosystems in the Balance - supporting future policy and research** on 22 and 23 January 2025.

The aim of the conference was to give infectious disease specialists and experts from the environmental sector an opportunity to engage with each other, creating space for dialogue across disciplines. It focused on five central themes: biodiversity loss, climate change, (illegal) wildlife trade, invasive alien species, and disease surveillance. Over a hundred participants from twelve countries, representing the public sector, the private sector, and research communities met in the heart of Brussels. The event catalysed new connections between health and environmental experts, laying the groundwork for future collaborations and more integrated research and policy approaches.

Several conclusions were reached, including:

- ▶ There is a need to generate more data, especially biodiversity and wildlife disease surveillance data.
- ▶ Equity and justice should be central to One Health policy, and local communities should be involved in setting priorities and selecting best practices to protect and restore ecosystems, which should be further supported by a fit-for-purpose and duly enforced legal framework.
- ▶ Global capacity-strengthening, education and awareness-building are highly important and can shape public opinion, which will have its impact on policy decisions.
- ▶ The outcomes were consolidated into a position paper ("*Ecosystems in the balance of One Health: recommendations for future policy and research*"), serving as a reference document for decision-making to the One Health community.

Participants at the One Health conference
Photo by Lise Goudeseune

PESC-RESPIN Joint Meeting

The Platform is actively involved in the **RESPIN project** and co-ordinates the **ECA Network**, which brings together IPBES National Focal Points and biodiversity platforms in the Europe and Central Asia region. In this capacity, the Platform co-organised the **PESC-RESPIN meeting** from 10 to 13 March 2025 in Brussels, bringing together stakeholders working at the science-policy interface on biodiversity and climate across Europe and Central Asia.

The meeting convened more than hundred participants, including National Focal Points from **IPBES** and **IPCC**, biodiversity and climate experts, representatives from the European Commission, and from organisations deeply engaged in linking environmental research with policy. This convergence created a space where IPBES and IPCC global assessment processes could be connected to national expertise and realities.

This meeting encouraged greater stakeholder participation, helped strengthen collaboration on biodiversity and climate research across the pan-European region, and explored practical ways to bridge national expertise with global processes.

By sharing knowledge and experiences, participants identified ways to enhance the preparation and adoption of expert reports, improve the integration of biodiversity and climate issues, and foster better dialogue between experts and decision-makers. They also explored how to mobilise experts and institutions more effectively and ensure that local knowledge and stakeholders are fully considered in international assessments.

This meeting reinforced the critical role of connecting national expertise with global biodiversity and climate processes. It was a powerful reminder of how important these gatherings are for shaping international biodiversity and climate agendas. And how collaboration, dialogue, and exchange at the regional and European level support the work of international platforms like IPBES and IPCC to contribute to shaping policies that reflect both scientific knowledge and practical realities on the ground.

Beautiful demoiselle (Calopteryx virgo)
Photo by [Erik Karitz, Pixabay](#)

Meadow Brown (Maniola jurtina)
Photo by [Ivan Samoshko, Unsplash](#)

Belgian IPBES Day

As the Belgian Focal Point to the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (**IPBES**), the Platform connects Belgian researchers, policymakers, and practitioners with IPBES processes and outcomes. This role was notably fulfilled through the organisation of the **Belgian IPBES Day** on 19 March in Brussels.

The uptake event centered on two landmark assessments adopted in late 2024: the Nexus Assessment, which explores the interconnections between biodiversity, water, food, health, and climate change, and the Transformative Change Assessment, which addresses the root causes of biodiversity loss and pathways towards a just and sustainable future.

Throughout the day, participants engaged directly with invited IPBES authors through keynote presentations, panel discussions, and interactive dialogues, creating a dynamic space for exchange between science and policy. The morning sessions offered in-depth insights into the assessments and explored the connections between them, while the afternoon shifted toward dialogue-based workshops based on five concrete use cases, translating the findings into practical applications within Belgian policy and practice.

By fostering exchanges across disciplines and sectors, the event strengthened the national uptake of global biodiversity knowledge and reinforced the Platform's role in bridging international scientific processes with local research, practice, and decision-making contexts.

*Participants at the Belgian IPBES Day
Photo by Lise Goudeseune*

DEVELOPING TOOLS IN SUPPORT OF DECISION-MAKING

In 2025, the Platform further advanced decision-making support tools that translate biodiversity science into actionable guidance for managers and policymakers, moving beyond data and advice provision towards operational decision support.

ManalAS

A standout example is **ManalAS**, an online decision support system developed during the **LIFE RIPARIAS project**. ManalAS is designed to assist biological invasions managers by helping them prioritise species of concern and priority areas for action, and to identify suitable management techniques in a transparent and spatially explicit way. Officially released at the end of 2024, the tool has since been further customised by the Platform to better serve Belgian contexts, while also exploring its applicability in other European Member States.

*RIPARIAS workflow
Illustration by Arnaud Monty*

ManalAS illustrates how the Platform translates scientific knowledge into practical, evidence-based workflows. By combining ecological data, management criteria, and strategic priorities, it guides resource allocation and planning in line with both national needs and EU requirements on biological invasions management. By embedding such systems in an open, user-oriented format, the Platform supports more consistent, transparent and repeatable decision-making, helping users turn complex biodiversity information into concrete, on-the-ground actions.

Looking ahead, the ManalAS experience opens promising perspectives for developing similar decision-support approaches in other biodiversity domains. Rather than replicating the system itself, the objective would be to apply the same philosophy (transparent criteria, robust evidence and user-oriented design) to support prioritisation and planning. This could potentially apply to ecological restoration, protected area management, monitoring strategies or nature-based solutions. By building on existing tools and filling the main gaps, the Platform can foster a coherent ecosystem of decision-support resources that make biodiversity knowledge more directly actionable.

FishBase & SeaLifeBase Symposium

FishBase and **SeaLifeBase** are globally recognised open-access information systems providing standardised, peer-reviewed data on fishes and other aquatic organisms. Widely used in biodiversity research, conservation and sustainable resource management, their trait and ecological data complement major global biodiversity infrastructures such as **GBIF**, **OBIS**, and **WoRMS**.

Building on Belgium's long-standing involvement in the FishBase Consortium, historically through the Royal Museum for Central Africa and more recently through the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences and Hasselt University as observer members, the Platform was part of the organisation of the **2025 FishBase Consortium Annual Meeting and Scientific Symposium** taking place in Brussels Belgium.

To strengthen connections with other data infrastructures and data types, the Platform actively engaged with the communities developing these two databases. In doing so, it consolidates its role as a science-policy interface by facilitating international collaboration, enhancing the visibility of Belgian biodiversity research, and strengthening links between global biodiversity data initiatives.

This support also drew on the Platform's data team's expertise and professional networks in FishBase and SeaLifeBase, while informing ongoing reflections on how future engagement with thematic knowledge systems could complement the Platform's core data activities centred on GBIF.

Gray Triggerfish (Balistes capriscus)

Photo by [Falk Viczian Solarboot-Projekte.gGmbH](#)
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SUPPORTING GLOBAL BIODIVERSITY INITIATIVES

Through the Platform, Belgium acts as a national focal point and facilitator for Belgian contributions to major global initiatives, such as GBIF, IUCN, and IPBES. By mobilising national expertise, the Platform contributes to the generation and dissemination of knowledge that informs global assessments, conservation priorities, and policy decisions. Our engagement ensures that Belgian researchers and institutions contribute to international biodiversity assessments and data infrastructures, and that national actions align with global biodiversity goals, the Platform also strongly promotes open access to biodiversity knowledge worldwide.

IUCN World Congress

The Platform serves as **Belgian Focal Point** for the **International Union for Conservation of Nature** (IUCN), world's oldest and largest environmental network of governmental, non-governmental, and Indigenous Peoples' organisations. Belgium currently counts **21 IUCN members** across multiple categories and the Platform carries out several strategic functions in support of the Union's work.

In October 2025, IUCN members gathered at the **World Conservation Congress**, in Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates. Following the successful **Regional Conservation Forum** organised in Belgium in 2024 by the Platform, Belgian members actively contributed to the Congress by submitting motions, delivering talks in the Congress Forum, and organising workshops. The Congress serves as the Union's main decision-making body, and this edition saw members approve the new IUCN vision and strategy for the next phase of its work.

As Belgian Focal Point, the Platform co-organised at the World Conservation Congress a workshop focused on realising and advancing the potential of IUCN Member Committees and raising their profile within the Union. The discussions highlighted the important role that Member Committees can play in bridging national expertise and action with international biodiversity processes. This illustrates how the Platform enables dialogue, strengthens coordination among actors, and contributes to collective approaches that advance global biodiversity priorities.

More broadly, this engagement reflects the Platform's role in linking national expertise with international biodiversity policy and action. By facilitating collaboration among Belgian IUCN members and actively contributing to discussions within the global IUCN network, the Platform ensures that Belgian knowledge, experience, and perspectives are reflected in broader conservation efforts.

Common Pochard (Aythya ferina)
Photo by SIA, iNaturalist
[CC BY 4.0](#)

GBIF: Enabling Open Science

The Platform serves as the **Belgian node** for the **Global Biodiversity Information Facility** (GBIF), an international open-data infrastructure that provides anyone, anywhere, with open access to data about all types of life on Earth.

In 2025, the Belgian contribution to this global initiative ranged from unique data mobilisation to implementing new international standards.

In a European context increasingly investing in harmonising biodiversity monitoring frameworks such as the European Biodiversity Observation Coordination Centre (EBOCC) and **Biodiversa+**, the Platform focused on the quality of information through enhancing data interoperability and reusability. A key achievement was the implementation of the **Humboldt extension** within monitoring datasets, allowing clearer, machine-readable documentation of sampling protocols and enabling the integration of survey data produced under different methodologies.

This pioneering work was presented at the **Living Data 2025 conference**, uniting the global **TDWG** (Biodiversity Information Standards), **GBIF**, **OBIS** (Ocean Biodiversity Information System), and **GeoBON** (Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network) communities under the theme "*Unified information driving transformation*". Belgian experts demonstrated how **FAIR** data infrastructures function not only as digital repositories, but as enablers of more coherent, scalable, and impactful biodiversity knowledge systems, catalysing social and ecological change.

Group photo at the Living Data Conference

EVIDENCE-BASED DECISION-MAKING ADVOCACY

One of the core priorities of the Platform is to strengthen evidence-based decision-making processes. In 2025, this was further reinforced through deeper engagement with the academic community, notably with the Université libre de Bruxelles becoming a host institute. This consolidated the Platform's capacity to connect scientific knowledge with policy- and practice-relevant needs, ensuring that evidence is not merely produced, but actively relied upon within decision-making processes.

In this context, the team actively showcased how the Platform contributes to evidence-based biodiversity governance in Belgium and internationally through IPBES. Throughout 2025, the Platform's added value became increasingly evident in making biodiversity data and knowledge more accessible, relevant, and usable, not only for decision-makers, but also for researchers seeking to engage with societal challenges and policy processes. This was achieved through conferences, seminars, and exchanges within research groups at ULB, UCLouvain, ULiège, and UGent working in natural sciences, but also at the invitation of faculties dealing with social sciences and humanities.

The issue of biological invasions was often used as a case study to illustrate the approach, as it highlights the complexity of decision-making across sectors, with a range of competent authorities and under conditions of uncertainty and illustrates why evidence matters. The topic also requires the mobilisation of diverse expertise from taxonomy and ecology to risk assessment, monitoring, management, and communication. By doing so, the Platform enables evidence-based decision-making through coordination, data and knowledge mobilisation, and the translation of scientific results into formats that can inform action at national and international levels.

These efforts made the Platform more visible within the academic world and emphasized the role of research institutions in supporting effective biodiversity governance. These efforts contributed to building a shared understanding that evidence-based decision-making is a necessary condition for biodiversity governance.

Beyond scientific contributions, by creating these connections, the Platform reaffirmed the necessity of aligning research outputs with societal and policy needs. For example, by engaging directly with early-career biologists at a key moment in their academic trajectory, the Platform raises awareness on how the science-policy and practice interface is an essential dimension of biodiversity work.

CONTRIBUTING TO IT OPEN-SOURCE DEVELOPMENT

IT development is a central component of the activities of the Platform. One of the key principles of the Platform's philosophy is openness, as it is reflected in the infrastructures it maintains and the tools it develops, both internally and in collaboration with external partners. The IT team actively contributes to the advancement and use of open-source tools. This involvement helps ensure that these tools remain relevant, efficient, and adaptable to evolving needs, while avoiding reliance on costly proprietary licenses. By contributing to shared tools, the work carried out within the Platform also benefits a wider community, reinforcing the sustainability of the open-source ecosystem.

Cartographic visualisation is essential for making biodiversity data accessible and directly usable by policymakers and practitioners. In 2025, developments carried out for the **ManalAS project** enabled the Platform to contribute to the evolution of the open-source mapping tool **Wegue**. Wegue is an open-source web mapping framework and library designed to support interactive geographic data visualisation. Through this work, the Platform's IT team strongly contributed to improvements of the software, enhancing its usability for biodiversity applications. These contributions strengthen Wegue's potential as a flexible foundation for future cartographic tools in the platform developments.

Southern Skimmer (Orthetrum brunneum)
Photo by [redhat, iNaturalist](#)
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UNLOCKING EVIDENCE DATA & KNOWLEDGE

Expanding biodiversity data

In 2025, the Platform placed a stronger focus on filling critical gaps in biodiversity knowledge, particularly in our understanding of under-represented taxonomic groups. By looking beyond well-documented and easily detectable species to more cryptic or historically overlooked organisms, the Platform is facilitating a transition toward more holistic, evidence-based conservation strategies that reflect more accurately the complexity of Belgian biodiversity.

A premier achievement of the year was the publication of the **Funbel (Fungi of Belgium) dataset**, which added 725,000 verified records to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). This milestone not only filled a targeted data gap but also marked the onboarding of a new strategic partner, the **Royal Flemish Mycological Society**. In parallel, the integration of advanced counting and DNA-based monitoring enabled the Platform to scale the **national data for bats** up to over 180,000 occurrences. These collaborative efforts were made possible through close collaboration with both institutional and non-institutional partners.

Clouded agaric (Clitocybe nebularis)
Photo by [Hans D., Pexels](#)

BiodivClim briefs

Within the framework of the **BiodivClim Cofund Action**, and in its capacity as a partner in the **Biodiversa+ partnership**, the Platform strengthened the uptake of research results by coordinating the development of knowledge

outputs, specifically in the form of briefs. In this context, the Platform led and oversaw the production of three issue briefs, synthesising the findings of twelve BiodivClim-funded projects into policy-relevant narratives.

The topics of the briefs were selected in alignment with current European policy priorities, ensuring both their strategic relevance and practical use in ongoing decision-making processes.

By translating complex research into accessible and actionable insights, these issue briefs support evidence-based decision-making for policymakers, land managers, researchers, and other stakeholders, by presenting them key findings on **Nature-based Solutions for European landscapes; soil biodiversity for climate, ecosystems, and agriculture;** and **mainstreaming resilience in forest policy.**

BiodivClim issue briefs by Biodiversa+

PUBLICATIONS

The Platform is a substantive contributor to the global scientific dialogue. Occupying a unique vantage point at the intersection of research and governance, it identifies the evolving needs of both spheres and actively works to synchronise them. By translating complex data into actionable insights, it continues to bridge the gap between scientific discovery and evidence-based policymaking.

In 2025, the team co-wrote the following publications:

Coleman, S., Heughebaert, A., Brosens, D. (2025). **Structuring Biological Survey Metadata for Reuse: Implementing the Humboldt Extension in Flemish Bird Monitoring Datasets on GBIF.** *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards*, 9, e180578. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.9.180578>

Garcia-Lozano, C., (...), **Vanderhoeven, S.,** et al. (2025). **Management Measures and Trends of Biological Invasions in Europe: A Survey-Based Assessment of Local Managers.** *Global Change Biology* 31(1), e70028. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70028>

Groom, Q., Adriaens, T., Davis, A., Desmet, P., Oldoni, D., Strubbe, D., Reyserhove, L., & **Vanderhoeven, S.** (2025). **How Open Science Builds Enduring Value for Biodiversity Research.** *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards*, 9, e183246. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.9.183246>

Groom, Q., Adriaens, T., Desmet, P., **Vanderhoeven, S.,** Yovcheva, N. (2025). **Why countries need the Global Biodiversity Information Facility: Lessons from Belgium [policy brief].** <https://zenodo.org/records/17023159>

Logghe, G., Batsleer, F., Maes, D., Permentier, T., Berg, M., Brosens, D., **Coleman, S.,** De Smedt, P., Hagge, J., Lambrechts, J., Pollet, M., Verheyde, F., & Bonte, D. (2025). **An in-depth dataset of northwestern European arthropod life histories and ecological traits.** *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 13, e146785. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.13.e146785>

Reniers, J., De Gruyter, J., Adriaens, T., **Vanderhoeven, S.,** Verreycken, H., Jacobs, A. (2025). **Understanding practices and awareness of recreational anglers regarding invasive alien species to support the development of biosecurity campaigns.** *Management of Biological Invasions*, 16(3), 677–698. <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2025.16.3.06>

Rymen, B., Heck, A., Elst N. (2025). Stop symptoombestrijding en gefragmenteerd biodiversiteitsbeleid - Stop à la lutte contre les symptômes et à la politique fragmentée en matière de biodiversité. *Science Connection*, 74, 24-29.
[Dutch version](#) [French version](#)

Verheyde, F., (...), Dekoninck, W., Coleman, S. & Mees, J. (2025). First comprehensive catalogue of hibernating Darwin wasps in the Western Palearctic (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 13, e176441. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.13.e176441>

Common kestrel (Falco tinnunculus)
Photo by [Franz W., Pixabay](#)

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BELGIAN SCIENCE POLICY OFFICE

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The Research Institute for Nature and Forest (**INBO**)

The Natural and Agricultural Environmental Studies Departement (**DEMNA**)

Sciensano (**Sciensano**)

Université Libre de Bruxelles (**ULB**)

Our Steering Committee is composed of BELSPO, the five host organisations, and the seven members hereunder. We would like to thank all of them for the strategic guidance they provide us with.

Scarce Swallowtail (Iphiclides podalirius)
Photo by Stijn Cooleman

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